

WORK MOTIVATION AND SUPERVISION OF WORK PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATION OFFICE EMPLOYEES IN TOMOHON CITY, INDONESIA

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Abstract

The low performance of education office employees in the city of Tomohon Indonesia may be caused by the low motivation of employees in carrying out their main duties and functions. This study aims to test whether there is a positive and significant correlation of work motivation to work performance, whether there is a positive and significant correlation of the influence of supervision on work performance, and whether there is a positive and significant correlation of the effect of work motivation and supervision simultaneously on the work performance of employees of the Education Office in Tomohon City Indonesia. The method used in this study is a survey method with a questionnaire data collection tool arranged in the form of a Likert scale. The study respondents were 68 employees who were drawn by random sampling. Face-to-face data collection was conducted with the consent of all private respondents. The analysis used to test the research hypothesis is a simple regression and correlation analysis technique, as well as multiple correlations for three variables. The conclusions of this study are (1) work motivation has a positive effect on the work performance of Tomohon City Education Office employees, (2) Supervision has a positive effect on the work performance of Tomohon City Education Office employees, and (3) work motivation and supervision simultaneously have a positive effect on the work performance of Tomohon City Education Office employees. It is recommended: (1) need to build mutual commitment among employees and superiors and always develop the ability to achieve in order to improve work performance, (2) need to cultivate motivation at work by providing compensation in accordance with employee work results in the form of rewards, and (3) improve employee work performance by changing the mindset where work is a form of worship to improve work-based management skills.

Keywords: Motivation, Supervision, Work Performance, Employees.

1. INTRODUCTION

The supervision process is a stage of control and evaluation to find out whether all activities have run in accordance with plan 1). In the Indonesian government system, the government responds to changes by conducting various government organizational restructurings aimed at improving employee performance as public servants based on a government system known as good governance in an effort to answer the demands of the wider community who want a good and correct government system based on principles rule of law, transparency, responsiveness and accountability.2). One of the government organizations located in Tomohon City, Indonesia, namely the Education Office which has the main function of developing and

supervising various activities of all existing educational institutions in order to support the achievement of national development goals, especially in preparing quality human resources (HR) with good intellectual and morality.

Theoretically, an employee will excel if he has the motivation to work where the motivation is built based on meeting various individual needs and interests. It is said that because the activities conducted by humans through organizations are aimed at fulfilling needs as a human being. 3). In other words, to be able to live a decent life humanly based on the nature of his humanity, man has needs that must be met. The ability to meet his needs is an important requirement in placing him in a position in accordance with the dignity and dignity as a human being who has the needs of security, future certainty, including obtaining adequate education, social needs including the need to be recognized / accepted and respected, the need for achievement or recognition and self-actualization.4).

Based on the results of Performance Appraisal conducted by the Audit Board of the Republic of Indonesia (BPK-RI) in Fiscal Year 2021 and Semester I of 2021 concluded that the performance results of the Tomohon City Education Office were still low on average. This situation is strongly suspected to be the result of low work motivation of employees and not optimal supervision conducted.5). The problem of low work motivation and supervisory functions that do not take place effectively that affect employee work performance, challenges researchers to study the problem more deeply through research to recommend alternative treatments further. Achievement in general can be interpreted as the relationship of results achieved with each resource used, where human resources play a significant role in improving performance. The real condition of achievement in this case is "efficient activities so as to get maximum results" 6).

The personnel department of the organization usually develops performance appraisals to employees in all departments. The main elements of this assessment system include: First, criteria that have to do with implementation. Second, the measures of such criteria, and then the provision of feedback to employees and personnel departments. Although the personnel department designs important systems, they rarely conduct real performance evaluations. This is why work performance problems often cannot be overcome seriously by organizations. Indeed, there are several factors that affect the achievement of work performance, including "ability factors: (ability) and motivational factors (motivation."7). This is in accordance with the opinion of Keith Davis, (motivation), who formulated that: (1) Human performance = Ability + Motivation, (2) Motivation = Attitude + Situation, (3) Ability = Knowledge + Skill .8).

Supervision is an activity or process to find out the results of implementation, errors, failures to improve then prevent the recurrence of errors, and is used as a "reference in correcting errors by studying the location of weaknesses or mistakes created to be corrected in the future". 9) Apart from references that examine the influence between work motivation, supervision, and work performance, it is also considered necessary to take a closer look at this problem in Tomohon City Indonesia. To answer the need to optimize employee performance for regional development through promotion for employees who have high work motivation and work

performance. Because the focus of this study is to examine whether there is a correlation between work motivation, supervision, and work performance of employees of the Tomohon City Education Office, Indonesia, there are three research problems that guide this study is whether there is a positive and significant correlation between work motivation and work performance? Is there a positive and significant correlation between supervision and work performance? and is there a positive and significant correlation between work motivation and simultaneous supervision of the work performance of employees of the Tomohon Indonesia city education office? To answer this research question, a survey research approach is used, 10)

2. METHODS

This study aims to describe whether there is a correlation between. Work motivation with work performance, whether there is a correlation between supervision and work performance and whether there is a correlation between work motivation and simultaneous supervision of the work performance of employees of the Tomohon City education office of Indonesia. To achieve this goal, a survey research approach is used with the consideration of researchers meeting directly with respondents, relatively small research budgets, data collection according to mechanisms, usefulness of significance, as well as small prejudices and accurate research results. 11).

Using safe sampling, 68 employees distributed questionnaires for three variables, 30 questions each in Indonesian and each was invited to fill out questionnaires on a Likert scale for four choices, namely from the numbers 1 Strongly Disagree, 2. Disagree Less, 3. Agree and 4. Totally agree. 12). The questionnaire for the Work Motivation variable is lifted from indicators: Not prioritizing personal interests or gologan, work commitment, continuous improvement, discipline on the job, working hard and being responsible. 13). The questionnaire for supervisory variables is raised from indicators of the preparation and implementation of work programs, guiding work implementation, guiding employees who experience work difficulties, guiding the use and maintenance of office infrastructure and facilities, and providing input or suggestions for leaders through reports on the results of task implementation. 14). While the work performance variable questionnaire is raised from the indicator that employees start working on time and finish on time, employees master their work, employees work according to their main duties and functions, when working employees build superior communication with subordinates and fellow employees, employees always follow the development of communication technology, and employees like to give input to the leadership. 15). In order for all questionnaires to be answered and collected again, our team conducts face-to-face meetings as well as provides an explanation of the research intent and technical filling of questionnaires after the completion of the supervisory coordination meeting. Field data were analyzed quantitatively using pearson correlation analysis by applying statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 21. 16)

2.1 Population and Sample

a. Populasi

Population is all characteristics related to these three research variables. As a population unit in this study are employees at the Education Office in Tomohon City totaling 208 employees.

b. Sample

By looking at the existing population, the sampling in this study was conducted randomly (random sampling) without paying attention to the strata in that population. While the sampling technique uses a formula developed by Slovin (in Riduwan. 17) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{N \cdot d^2 + 1}$$

Information:

n = Number of samples

N = Total population = 208

D2 = Precision set 10%

Using a precision of 0.1 is obtained:

$$n = \frac{208}{208(0,1)^2 + 1}$$

= 67.53. So the study sample was set at 68 people

2.2 Data Analysis Techniques

Collected data analyzed using statistics as follows: (1) description of data consisting of frequency distribution and histogram, (2) analysis prerequisite testing, namely testing analysis requirements, namely normality testing, (3) hypothesis testing is carried out using regression analysis and multiple correlations. 18).

Hipotesis Statistik

Based on the research hypothesis that has been proposed, it is necessary to put forward the pair of hypotheses tested.

The pairs of statistical hypotheses and alternative hypotheses tested are as follows.

1. $H_0 : \rho_{yx1} \leq 0$
 $H_1 : \rho_{yx1} > 0$
2. $H_0 : \rho_{yx2} \leq 0$
 $H_1 : \rho_{yx2} > 0$
3. $H_0 : \rho_{yx12} \leq 0$
 $H_1 : \rho_{yx12} > 0$

3. RESULTS OF AND DISCUSSION

The study consisted of three variables, with details: two independent variables and one dependent variable. The dependent variable is Work Performance which is given Y notation while the independent variable is work motivation with X1 symbol and supervision with X2 notation. To get an overview of research data from each variable, the following data is presented through descriptive statistics, namely the frequency distribution of each variable.

3.1 Work Performance (Y)

The research instrument is a questionnaire for work performance variables that have been compiled and tested, producing 30 valid statements from 31 items tested. Thus, theoretically the respondents' answer scores are in the range between 30 – 150.

Based on research data, it is known that the empirical score is in the range of 73 - 138. Making frequency distributions is done by dividing distribution classes into seven classes whose presentation can be seen in table 4.1.

Based on the list of frequency distributions, the most data is in the range of 101-110 with an absolute frequency of 17 or with a relative frequency of 25%, followed by data in the range of 111-120 with an absolute frequency of 13 or a relative frequency of 19.12%. The absolute frequency of the next sequence is in the range of 91-100 with an absolute frequency of 11 or with a relative frequency of 16.18.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Work Performance Variable Data (Y)

No.	Interval Class	Frequency		
		Absolute	Relative (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	71 – 80	4	5,88	5,88
2	81 – 90	8	11,76	17,64
3	91 – 100	11	16,18	33,82
4	101-110	17	25,00	58,82
5	111-120	13	19,12	77,94
6	121-130	9	13,24	91,18
7	131-140	6	8,82	100,00
Sum		68	100	-

Then followed by frequencies in other interval classes, until the lowest is the frequency in the interval class in the range of 71-80 whose absolute frequency is 4 or a relative frequency of 5.88%.

The state of the research data after being made in the histogram can be seen in the following figure:

3.2 Work Motivation (X1)

The preparation of research instruments is based on research variable indicators, namely work motivation variables. The research instrument is a questionnaire for work motivation variables that has been compiled and tested, producing 30 valid statements from 34 items compiled and tested. Thus, theoretically the respondent's answer score is in the range between 30 - 150. Based on research data, it is known that the empirical score is in the range of 71 - 140. Making frequency distributions is done by dividing distribution classes into seven classes whose presentation can be seen in table 4.2.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Work Motivation Variable Data (X1)

No.	Interval Class	Frequency		
		Absolute	Relative (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	71 – 80	5	7,35	7,35
2	81 – 90	9	13,24	20,59
3	91 – 100	12	17,65	38,24
4	101-110	15	22,06	60,3
5	111-120	11	16,18	76,48
6	121-130	9	13,24	89,71
7	131-140	7	10,29	100,00
Sum		68	100	-

Based on the list of frequency distributions, the most data is in the range of 101-110 with an absolute frequency of 15 or with a relative frequency of 22.06%, followed by data in the range of 91-100 with an absolute frequency of 12 or a relative frequency of 17.65%. The absolute frequency of the next sequence in the range 111-120 with an absolute frequency of 11 or with a relative frequency of 16.18.

Then followed by frequencies in other interval classes, until the lowest is the frequency in the interval class in the range of 71-80 whose absolute frequency is 5 or a relative frequency of 7.35%.

The state of the research data after being made in the histogram can be seen in the following figure:

Table 3

No.	Variable	L-table (a=0.05)	L-count	Information
1	Work Performance (Y)	0,1074	0,0711	Normal
2	Work Motivation (X1)	0,1074	0,0743	Normal
3	Surveillance (X2)	0,1074	0,0827	Normal

3.3 Supervision

The research instrument is a questionnaire for supervisory variables that have been compiled and tested, producing 30 valid statements from 32 items tested. Thus, theoretically the respondent's answer score is in the range between 30-150.

Based on research data, it is known that the empirical score is in the range of 70 - 139. Making frequency distribution is done by dividing the distribution class into seven classes whose presentation can be seen in table 4.

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Supervisory Variable Data (X2)

No.	Interval Class	Frequency		
		Absolute	Relative (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	70 – 79	4	5,88	5,88
2	80 – 89	8	11,76	17,64
3	90 – 99	12	17,65	35,29
4	100-109	16	23,53	58,82
5	110-119	13	19,12	77,94
6	120-129	9	13,24	91,18
7	130-139	6	8,82	100,00
Sum		68	100	-

Based on the list of frequency distributions, it can be seen that the most data is in the range of 100-109 with an absolute frequency of 16 or with a relative frequency of 23.53%, followed by data in the range of 110-119 with an absolute frequency of 13 or a relative frequency of 19.12%. The absolute frequency of the next sequence in the range of 90-99 with an absolute frequency of 12 or with a relative frequency of 17.65%.

Then followed by frequencies in other interval classes, until the lowest is the frequency in the interval class in the range 70-79 whose absolute frequency is 4 or a relative frequency of 5.88%.

Data Normality Test

One of the requirements in the use of test statistics that are classified as parametric is the normality test. This test is carried out to ascertain whether the data collected from respondents comes from a normally distributed population or not. A test that is often used to test data normality is the Lilliefors test. One of the advantages of this normality test is the use of the z distribution list for data normality calculations. The hypotheses that guide this test are:

Ho: $L\text{-count} < L\text{-table}$ = data derived from normally distributed populations

H1: $L\text{-count} > L\text{-table}$ = data comes from a population not normally distributed

Based on the research data, it can be tested and explained the state of normality test data for each research variable as follows:

a. Normality of Work Performance Variables

From the results of testing the normality of data on work performance variables, in accordance with the results of data analysis, the L-count statistic was obtained which was 0.0711 while the significant value of Lilliefors with df.68 for n = 68 at $\alpha=0.05$ was 0.1074. This value is much greater when compared to the value of L-count = 0.0711. So H0 is accepted and rejects Ha. Thus, it can be concluded that the data of job performance variables come from a normally distributed population.

b. Normality of Work Motivation Variables

From the results of testing data normality based on the results of the analysis, the L-count statistic was obtained which was 0.0743 while the significant value of Lilliefors with df.68 for n = 68 with $\alpha = 0.05$ obtained a result of 0.1074. This value is much greater when compared to $\alpha = 0.05$. So H0 is accepted and rejects Ha. Thus, it can be concluded that the data of work motivation variables come from a normally distributed population.

c. Normality of Supervisory Variables

From the results of testing data normality based on the results of the analysis, the L-count statistic was obtained which was 0.0827 while the significant value of Lilliefors with $\alpha = 0.05$ for n = 68 obtained a result of 0.1074. This value is much greater when compared to the value of L-count = 0.827. So H0 is accepted and rejects Ha. Thus, it can be concluded that the surveillance variable data comes from a normally distributed population.

Based on the test results about normality for the three research variables, everything is normal. Or in other words that the data collected comes from a normally distributed population.

Normality Test Results Summary

Test Linearity and Meaningfulness of Regression as Analysis Requirements

To obtain the magnitude as demanded by the variance analysis table, it is necessary to calculate the following quantities:

$$JK (T) = \sum Y^2 = 859263$$

$$JK(A) = (\sum Y)^2 = 836136.10 \quad (6130) (8529)$$

$$JK (b/a) = 0.500 (521844) = 8372.215$$

$$68$$

$$JK (S) = 859263 - 836136.104 - 8372.215$$

$$= 14754.681$$

$$JK (G) = 10045.12$$

$$JK (TC) = 14754.681 - 10045.12$$

$$= 6949.35$$

Table 5: Analysis of Variance for Significance and Linearity of Work Motivation Regression on Job Performance $\hat{Y} = 48.556 + 0.500X_1$

Sources of variation	Dk	JK	RJK	F-count	F-table	
					$\alpha = 0,05$	$\alpha = 0,01$
Total	68	859263				
Coefficient (a)	1	836136,10				
Regresi (b/a)	1	6132,43	6132,43	30,67	3,96	6,96
Waste	66	16994,47	199,93			
Tuna fit	27	6949,35	257,38	1,05	1,66	2,06
Error	41	10045,12	245,00			

Information:

** Significant regression at real level $\alpha = 0.05$ or $\alpha = 0.01$

* The regression direction is linear in real level $\alpha = 0.01$.

Before being used for drawing conclusions, this regression equation needs to be tested for the degree of significance and linearity. The test was conducted using the variance analysis table which can be seen in table 4.5.

Through the test results about significance and linearity, the regression equation tested is linear and significant. Therefore, the regression equation obtained through the results of data analysis, namely $\hat{Y} = 48.556 + 0.500X_1$, is used to draw conclusions. Through these results, it can be explained that an increase in one unit of work motivation will be followed by an increase in employee work performance. The magnitude of the increase in employee performance with increased work motivation can be explained by the regression equation that has been obtained, namely $\hat{Y} = 48.556 + 0.500X_1$.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance for Significance and Linearity of Supervisory Regression of Job Performance $\hat{Y} = 39.255 + 0.699X_2$

Sources of variation	Dk	JK	RJK	F-count	F-table	
					$\alpha = 0,05$	$\alpha = 0,01$
Total	68	859263				
Coefficient (a)	1	836136,10				
Regression (b/a)	1	6710,86	6710,86	34,75	3,96	6,96
Waste	66	16416,04	193,13			
Tuna fit.	31	7183,03	221,37	1,39	1,67	2,08
Error	37	8233,01				

Information:

** Significant regression at real level $\alpha = 0.05$ or $\alpha = 0.01$

* The regression direction is linear at the real level $\alpha = 0.01$.

Before being used for drawing conclusions, this regression equation needs to be tested for the degree of significance and linearity. The test was conducted using the variance analysis table which can be seen in table 4.6.

Through the test results about significance and linearity, it can be said that the regression equation tested is linear and significant. Therefore, the regression equation obtained through the results of data analysis is $\hat{Y} = 39.255 + 0.699X_2$ to draw conclusions. Through these results, it can be explained that an increase in one unit of supervision unit will be followed by an increase in employee work performance. The magnitude of the increase in employee performance with increased supervision can be explained by the regression equation that has been obtained, namely $\hat{Y} = 39.255 + 0.699X_2$.

3.4 The Effect of Supervision on Work Performance

Based on the results of data analysis on supervision with work performance, the regression equation $\hat{Y} = 19.055 + 0.820X$ was obtained. This regression equation explains the coefficient of contribution of supervisory variables with work performance if the score or magnitude of the value of the variable changes either increasing or decreasing. However, before being used in order to draw conclusions, it is necessary to first examine the meaningfulness of the contribution of supervisory variables to work performance variables.

Based on the test results on the meaningfulness of the regression equation, $F_h = 114.340$ was obtained. With an error rate of 0.0001 or 0.001%. This value indicates that the supervisory variable studied whose contribution to work performance cannot be ignored, so the hypothesis that there is an effect of supervision on job performance can be accepted with $\alpha = 0.05$.

The results of data analysis on supervision contribute to work performance, if the work motivation variable as a control variable, obtained the result $r^2_{Y_{2.1}} = 0.303$. When looking at the results of the t test shows that t count is = 6.957 and t is significant = 0.001 smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Since the calculated price t is greater than the table t, the hypothesis that there is an effect of supervision on work performance is acceptable.

If there is an erroneous conclusion in accepting the research hypothesis that has been proposed, then the chance of error that occurs is $p = 0.0001$. Because of the small error, it can be used as a basis for accepting research hypotheses.

3.5 The Effect of Work Motivation and Supervision on Work Performance.

Based on the results of data analysis on the simultaneous contribution (together) of work motivation variables and supervision with work performance, a regression equation was obtained $\hat{Y} = 20.877 + 0.492X_1 + 0.312X_2$.

This regression equation explains the coefficient of contribution of each variable to work performance if the score or magnitude of the value of the variables in question changes either increasing or decreasing. But before being used in order to draw conclusions, it is first necessary to examine the meaningfulness of the contribution of each variable with work performance variables. Regarding the results of the analysis of the degree of simultaneous determination of work motivation and supervision variables with work performance of $R^2 = 0.648$ with a large correlation coefficient of $R = 0.805$. Based on the test results on the meaningfulness of the regression equation, $F_h = 59.804$ was obtained. With an error rate of 0.0001 or 0.001%. This value implies that of the two variables studied their contribution to

work performance cannot be ignored, so the hypothesis that there is an influence of work motivation and supervision on work performance can be accepted with $\alpha = 0.05$.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 The Effect of Work Motivation on Work performance

Based on the results of data analysis, the research hypothesis that states that there is an influence of work motivation on work performance is acceptable. Data analysis gives X influence results₁ against Y is mean.

This effect based on F test statistics turned out to be meaningful. The results of this data analysis explain that work motivation makes a meaningful contribution to work performance. A view that puts forward that "motivation enables a person to realize the work-related tasks necessary to achieve a goal". In this regard, employees as people responsible for carrying out tasks in the administrative field must have motivation in accordance with their field of duty in order to realize organizational goals. 18). Employees must have and master knowledge, skills and behavior that are in accordance with the duties they carry. So that the research hypothesis that says that employee work motivation provides a meaningful relationship to work performance cannot be denied, because employees in order to achieve good work results, employees must have and master knowledge and skills that are in accordance with the tasks that have been assigned to them.

Thus, motivation is a skill that must be performed by someone who works in a particular administrative field, which describes the actions, behaviors, and results that must be demonstrable by that person. Hence, motivation is not only extrinsic but also intrinsic. Meanwhile, the achievement of an employee will be optimal if supported by sufficient ability and high work drive. To achieve high achievements both in the fields of administrative, education and teaching, the fields of research and scientific activities, social activities and community service, a certain number of skills is needed to do so. 19). although many factors determine the achievement of achievement, work motivation is the main factor that determines the most. Thus, it makes sense that an employee is required to have work motivation. On that basis, the hypothesis that says that there is a relationship between work motivation and work performance cannot be ignored.

4.2 The Effect of Supervision on Work Performance.

Based on the results of data analysis, the research hypothesis that states that there is an influence of supervision on work performance is acceptable. Data analysis gives a result between X₂, and Y is meaningful.

This effect based on F test statistics turned out to be meaningful. The results of this data analysis explain that supervision makes a meaningful contribution to work performance. Supervision is an activity or process to find out the results of implementation, errors, failure to improve then prevent the recurrence of errors. Therefore, there needs to be a reference.

In correcting errors by studying the location of weaknesses or errors created for later correction".20). Thus, the higher an employee's assessment of the supervision in which he or she works, the higher their sense of unity, the higher their desire to innovate and the higher their efforts to achieve results through cooperation. Achievement is a process of achieving and maintaining behaviors that lead to the achievement of results.

Work performance is an emotional response about work and how well the results are achieved on various dimensions which include (1) the job itself, (2) salary and (3) co-worker relationships. 21). Therefore, the higher the employee's evaluation of supervision, the higher their enthusiasm to innovate, result-oriented and member-oriented. Increased enthusiasm to innovate, member-oriented will be able to improve work performance which eventually employees will get satisfaction from the success of their own work. Supervision, which is the prevention of errors in the implementation of work in the organization and oriented towards fellow members, will create a conducive atmosphere in the body of the organization and this will be able to improve work performance. This is proven by the results of data analysis on the contribution of supervision to employee achievement, which is $r^2_{Y2.1} = 0.303$. Although the contribution is small, it cannot be ignored because the result t count of = 6.957 is greater than the price t significant = 0.0001 is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Because the calculated price of t is greater than t significant, the hypothesis that supervision has a positive and significant relationship to job performance at the Education Office in Manado City cannot be ignored.

The results of the analysis can also be explained that supervision at work is particularly important, someone whose performance is good will not be separated from the innovation process in him to be expressed positively through work in improving work performance.

4.3 Effect of Work Motivation and Supervision to Work performance

Based on the results of data analysis, about the simultaneous contribution (together) of work motivation variables and supervision with work performance, the regression equation $\hat{Y} = 20,877 + 0.492X_1 + 0.312X_2$ was obtained.

This regression equation explains the coefficient of contribution of each variable to work performance if the score or magnitude of the value of the variables in question changes either increasing or decreasing. However, before being used in order to draw conclusions, it is first necessary to examine the meaningfulness of the contribution of each variable to the variable of work performance.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis, the following can be concluded:

- 1) Employee motivation has an influence on work performance. This means that employees in carrying out their job duties, need work motivation so that they can improve employee

work performance.

- 2) Supervision is a positive effort in mobilizing, mobilizing and directing all the resources and potential of human resources of an organization so that they can excel.
- 3) Motivation and supervision are simultaneously proven to improve employee performance when a humane approach is taken by prioritizing aspects of meeting the intrinsic and external needs of employees. For this reason, it is recommended to build mutual commitment among employees and superiors and always develop the ability to excel in improving work performance. Furthermore, cultivating work motivation by providing compensation in accordance with employee work results, developing a fair and transparent career system, and rewarding outstanding employees and providing sanctions for employees who perform below standard or violate regulations at work.

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